

FARMERS' AND DEALERS' PERCEPTION TOWARDS NANO FERTILIZERS IN BHANDARA DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study investigates farmers' and dealers' perception towards nano fertilizers in Bhandara district of Maharashtra. Nano fertilizers are synthesized or modified versions of fertilizers, developed using nanotechnology. Due to their increased surface area to volume ratio, nano fertilizers exhibit high availability and absorption rates, enabling more efficient uptake by leaves, which in turn enhances photosynthesis and biomass production for healthier crops. For the present study, nearly 60 farmers and 15 dealers from various talukas of the district were selected. This district was purposefully selected based on the number of farmers using nano fertilizers and the number of dealers selling nano fertilizers.

The findings revealed that the selected farmers who applied nano fertilizers to their fields observed improvements in crop yields, while the dealers who sold these fertilizers reported positive outcomes from their customers use. Among the selected farmers, a large proportion were well educated, having completed higher secondary education or beyond, which likely contributed to their willingness to adopt new technologies and make informed agricultural decisions. The dealers were well aware of nano fertilizers, with most acknowledging the benefits of selling them, though price sensitivity and availability remained key considerations. The majority of dealers had positive experiences with nano fertilizers, indicating their growing popularity over time.

However, some farmers faced problems in application of nano fertilizers in field. This paper discusses the difficulties faced by farmers and identifying advantages of nano fertilizers.

Keywords: Farmers, dealers, nano fertilizers, nano urea, nano DAP, perception.

Introduction

Nitrogenous fertilizers remain the key input, critical for augmenting sustainable high crop production. Its role in utilisation of the full yield potential of crops is sufficiently documented. Efficiency of currently used nitrogenous fertilizer is quite low. Current use efficiency of fertilizers is low being 40–50% for N and 2-5 % for micronutrients such as iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), and boron (B). It offers a vast scope to improve the low nutrient use efficiency (NUE). Excessive use of fertilizer increases economic cost of product and also dents the farmer's income. In retrospect, excessive use of fertilizers and their losses from root zone are the cause of soil, water and air pollution. To address this issue, nutrient supply needs to be synchronised with crop demand which has a potential of reduction in nutrient losses with improvement in NUE. For this several measures have been adopted world over but research and development of fertilizers have not been adequate enough to economically address this issue effectively. As the global population is increasing, the demand for food is also increasing day by day, which has increase the large-scale use of fertilizers. For solving these problems in crop production nano-fertilizers, pesticides and herbicides may be effective tools in agriculture for better pest and nutrient management.

Nano fertilizers is a new technology that can help in decreasing the large-scale use of fertilizers and also good for soil, crop, and the environment. The size of a nanomaterial is typically about 1 to 100 nano meters. They can be naturally occurring or engineered. responsive crop varieties. Among mineral nutrients, nitrogen is the first and foremost nutrient required for crop plants as it is the constituent of chlorophyll and many proteins and enzymes and thus plays a significant role during the vegetative growth of crops.

Nano fertilizers are synthesized or modified form of traditional fertilizers developed with the help of a nanotechnology. Nano fertilizers include two forms of fertilizers i.e. nano urea & nano DAP. Nano fertilizers are highly dynamic and differ from conventional fertilizers due to their nanoscale size. Their increased surface area to volume ratio enhances their availability and absorption, allowing for more efficient uptake by soil and leaves, which results in increased photosynthesis and biomass production for healthier crops. Foliar-applied nano fertilizers (nano urea & nano DAP) boost nutrient uptake efficiency (NUE) and improve the nutritional quality of crops through biofortification. Nanotechnology-based nano-nitrogen offers a promising alternative to reduce farmers dependence on urea. Nano urea has several benefits like it is inexpensive and simple to transport

between locations, it saves the environment and lessens the need for chemical fertilizer in the field, use of nano urea results in higher agricultural yield and greater food quality, nano urea reduces the need for urea by 50% while giving the plant 80% of the nitrogen they need, nano urea protects the quality of ground water, good towards sustainable development and reduces global warming. By applying nano urea as a foliar spray, urea losses can be minimized, due to the ultra-small size and surface properties, the nano urea liquid gets absorbed by plants more effectively when sprayed on their leaves.

Nano DAP, the second liquid nano fertilizer, contains up to 8% nitrogen and 16% phosphorus, and is applied as a foliar spray. Its unique properties enhance plant performance by improving absorption, increasing yield, promoting photosynthesis, and expanding leaf surface area. Nano fertilizers (such as nano urea and nano DAP) deliver nutrients more efficiently to plants due to their nanoscale size, allowing for better absorption through roots and leaves. This results in more precise nutrient delivery and can reduce the overall fertilizer requirements for crops. Various trials conducted on different crops across multiple locations have shown that nano fertilizers can produce higher yields compared to conventional granular fertilizers.

This study examined the farmers' and dealers' perception towards nano fertilizers in Bhandara district of Maharashtra, as well as how various socioeconomic attributes impact purchase behaviour of farmers. This study has been conducted with the following objectives;

1. To study the socioeconomic attributes of the selected farmers in Bhandara district
2. To study the factors associated with purchase of nano fertilizers by farmers in Bhandara district
3. To assess the dealers preference towards the selling of nano fertilizers in Bhandara district.

Methodology**Study area**

The present study was conducted in Bhandara district of Maharashtra during 2023-24. Bhandara district faces problems of unpredictable rainfall, floods, poor yield in agricultural sector. This district was selected purposively based on the number of farmers that use nano fertilizers and various dealers that sell nano fertilizers. The primary data was collected using a survey method. Out of the seven talukas in Bhandara district, 3 talukas, Lakhandur, Lakhani and Sakoli, were selected. Total 60 farmers were selected from 3 talukas of Bhandara District, Lakhandur, Lakhani and Sakoli, from each taluka 2 villages are selected, from each village 10 farmers are selected. Total 15 dealers

were selected from 3 talukas of Bhandara district, Lakhandur, Lakhani and Sakoli, and from each taluka 5 dealers were selected from different villages of talukas.

Analysis of data

Percentage tabular analysis is done to know the socioeconomic attributes of the selected farmers, factors associated with purchase of nano fertilizers by farmers, assess the dealers preference towards the selling of nano fertilizers. Statistical tools such as percentages were used to summarize the data, providing clear insights.

Results and Discussion

Socioeconomic Attributes of the Selected Farmers

The socioeconomic attributes of the selected farmers in Bhandara district of Maharashtra are presented in Table No. 1.

From the selected 60 farmers most farmers have small to marginal landholdings, with 36.7% small and 30% marginal, 10% farmers have medium landholdings while only 1.6% have large landholdings.

From the selected 60 farmers majority of farmers are middle-aged 41-60 yrs majority (50%), followed by young farmers (46.66%), as a result majority of middle aged farmers are in the Bhandara district.

In terms of education the majority of farmers are educated, with 45% being graduates, followed by 41.66% with HSC qualifications.

Among the selected farmers most families (81.67%) are medium-sized, consisting of 4-7 members, while a small percentage (8.33%) have fewer than 3 members. joint families dominate (80%), with only 20% living in nuclear families. This shows that majority of the farmers lived in joint families and it helped them in farming operations.

Among the selected farmers (38.33%) earn between ₹50,001-₹100,000 annually, while 20% earn less than ₹50,000. 30.33% farmers 18 earn between 100001-300000 this shows that most farmers are middle income farmers.

From the selected farmers agriculture is the primary occupation for 73.33% of farmers. Some supplement their income with other activities, like shopkeeping or rice trading.

This profile highlights that most farmers in the sample are small-scale, middle-aged, educated, and part of joint families, with agriculture as their main occupation.

Due to weather and soil conditions, rice is the most widely grown crop in the Bhandara district of Maharashtra state. Farmers also grow sugarcane and vegetables.

Table No. 1 Socioeconomic Attributes of the Selected Farmers

Sr. No.	Factors	No of Farmers (n=60)
1	Landholding	
	Marginal (Upto 1 Ha)	18 (30.00)
	Small (1.01-2Ha)	22 (36.70)
	Semi Medium (2.01-4 Ha)	13 (21.70)
	Medium (4.01-10 Ha)	6 (10.00)
	Large (Greater than 10 Ha)	1 (1.60)
2	Age	
	Young (21-40)	28 (46.66)
	Middle Age (41-60)	30 (50.00)
	Old (61-70)	2 (3.33)
	Education	
3	Illiterate	0 (0.00)
	SSC	4 (6.66)
	HSC	25 (41.66)
	Graduate	27 (45.00)
	Post Graduate	4 (6.66)
4	Family Size	
	Small (Upto 3)	5 (8.33)
	Medium (4-7)	49 (81.67)
	Large (More than 7)	6 (10.00)
	Type of Family	
5	Nuclear Family	12 (20.00)
	Joint Family	48 (80.00)
6	Annual Income	
	Upto 50000	12 (20.00)

	50001-100000	23 (38.33)
	100001-300000	18 (30.00)
	300001-500000	7 (11.66)
7	Occupation (Main & Sub)	
	Agriculture	44 (73.33)
	Agriculture & Shop	7 (11.66)
	Agriculture & Rice Trader	4 (6.66)
	Agriculture & Service	2 (3.33)
	Agriculture & Other	3 (5.00)

(Figures in parentheses indicates percentage of total socioeconomic attributes of farmers)

3.2 Factors Associated with Purchase of Nano Fertilizers by Farmers

The factors associated with purchase of nano fertilizers in terms of season, price, dealers perception, brand reputation by farmers in Bhandara district of Maharashtra are presented in Table No. 2.

In terms of season most farmers 25 in number prefer the kharif (41.66%) and 24 farmers prefer summer (40%) season, while rabi season preference is lower only 11 farmers prefer it (18.33%).

Price is the factor which is most important in purchasing any product.

Majority of 33 farmers perceive the price as medium (55%), with 20

farmers (33.33%) considering it low and only 7 farmers (11.67%) has no problem with high price.

Over 33 farmers said that in terms of dealers perception in purchasing nano fertilizers (55%) they observe good sales, while 27 farmers (45%) has no problem with average sales and they not consider it as a major concern. Relationship with the dealers play an important role deciding purchase behaviour of farmers.

Farmers are fairly split on brand reputation, with 28 farmers (46.66%) said that good reputation of the product is important and 32 farmers (53.33%) considering that average reputation is also considerable.

Table No. 2 Factors associated with purchase of nano fertilizers in terms of season, price, dealers perception, brand reputation

Sr. No.	Factors	No of Farmers (n=60)
1	Season	
	Kharif	25 (41.66)
	Rabi	11 (18.33)
	Summer	24 (40.00)
2	Price	
	Low	20 (33.33)
	Medium	33 (55.00)
	High	7 (11.67)
3	Dealers Perception	
	Good Sale	33 (55.00)
	Average Sale	27 (45.00)
4	Brand Reputation	
	Good	28 (46.66)
	Average	32 (53.33)

(Figures in parentheses indicates percentage of total factors associated with purchase of nano fertilizers)

The factors associated with purchase of nano fertilizers in terms of timely availability, cost saving & result in Bhandara district of Maharashtra are presented in Table No. 3.

During the cropping season most of the 36 farmers (60%) indicated timely availability of products is important, while 24 farmers (40%) said that delays or unavailability is not a major problem.

A significant majority 45 of farmers (75%) feel that cost savings is necessary, remaining 15 farmers (25%) not consider it as a important factor.

Among the selected 60 farmers 12 farmers (76.66%) of farmers said that positive results are important in their usage of nano fertilizers, whereas other 14 farmers (23.34%) did not consider it as a major concern.

This data highlights that farmers are generally satisfied with pricing, dealer performance, and product outcomes, although some challenges exist in availability and brand reputation.

Table No. 3 Factors associated with purchase of nano fertilizers in terms of timely availability, cost saving & result

Sr. No.	Factors	No of Farmers (n=60)
1	Timely Availability	
	Yes	36 (60.00)
	No	24 (40.00)
2	Cost Saving	
	Yes	45 (75.00)
	No	15 (25.00)
3	Result	
	Yes	46 (76.66)
	No	14 (23.34)

(Figures in parentheses indicates percentage of total factors associated with purchase of nano fertilizers)

3.3 To Assess the Dealers Preference Towards the Selling of Nano Fertilizers

Dealers preference towards the selling of nano fertilizers in terms of economic feasibility, price, availability Bhandara district of Maharashtra are presented in Table No. 4.

Economic feasibility means when they go to purchase it should be available, out of the selected dealers 11 dealers (73.33%) said that economic feasibility of nano fertilizers is important, remaining 4 dealers (26.66%) do not consider it as a important factor. Effect of price during purchase of nano fertilizers by dealers is a major factor 9 dealers

(60.00%) believe that the price of nano fertilizers affects their purchasing decisions, remaining 6 dealers (40.00%) do not think that the price has a significant impact on their purchasing decisions.

Similar to pricing, 9 dealers (60%) said that the nano fertilizers availability in cropping season should be on time, remaining 6 dealers (40%) said that availability is not on time then it is not a concern. This indicates that most dealers find the products to be economically viable and reasonably priced, though there are concerns about availability for a significant portion of them.

Table No. 4 Dealers preference towards the selling of nano fertilizers in terms of economic feasibility, price, availability

Sr. No.	Factors	No of Dealers (n=15)
1	Economic Feasibility	
	Yes	11 (73.33)
	No	4 (26.66)
2	Price	
	Yes	9 (60.00)
	No	6 (40.00)
3	Availability	
	Yes	9 (60.00)
	No	6 (40.00)

(Figures in parentheses indicates percentage of total dealers preference towards selling of nano fertilizers)

3.4. Distribution of dealers in terms of result between granular fertilizers and nano fertilizers

Table No. 5 presents distribution of dealers on the results of nano fertilizers and granular fertilizers across three talukas: Lakhandur, Lakhani, and Sakoli. The data is based on responses from 15 dealers. From the selected 15 dealers in different talukas of Bhandara district Lakhandur, Lakhani, Sakoli. In Lakhandur taluka 3 dealers says positive results of Nano Fertilizers, remaining 2 observed good results of granular fertilizers. Lakhani taluka 4 dealers have observed good

results in nano fertilizers, remaining 1 dealers observed good results in granular fertilizers. Sakoli taluka shows that 3 dealers observed good results of nano fertilizers, 2 dealers observed good results in granular fertilizers. It is a major concern because dealers observe results and then buy fertilizer. Overall majority of dealers observed good results of nano fertilizer and preferred nano fertilizers over granular fertilizers, with nano fertilizers consistently yielding better results according to their feedback.

Table No. 5 Distribution of dealers on the results of nano fertilizers and granular fertilizers

Sr. No	Name of Taluka	Result of Nano Fertilizers	Result of Granular Fertilizers	No of Dealers (n=15)
1	Lakhandur	3	2	5 (33.33)
2	Lakhani	4	1	5 (33.33)
3	Sakoli	3	2	5 (33.33)

(Figures in parentheses indicates percentage of total distribution of dealers on the results of nano fertilizers and granular fertilizers)

3.5. Distribution of dealers in terms of sale between granular fertilizers and nano fertilizers

Table No. 6 outlines the distribution of dealer preferences between the sale of nano fertilizers and granular fertilizers across three talukas: Lakhandur, Lakhani, and Sakoli. The data is based on responses from 15 dealers, equally distributed across the talukas.

3 Dealers from Lakhandur taluka show their preference towards nano fertilizers, 2 dealers show preference towards granular fertilizers. 4 dealers from Lakhani show their preference towards nano fertilizers, 1 dealer shows preference towards granular fertilizers. In Sakoli taluka 3 dealers show their preference towards nano fertilizers, 2 dealers show preference towards granular fertilizers. Each taluka has an equal number of dealers (5), and the percentage distribution among the

Table No. 6 Distribution of dealers preference towards sale of granular fertilizers and nano fertilizers

Sr. No	Name of Taluka	Dealer Preference Toward Sale of Nano Fertilizer	Dealer Preference Toward Sale of Granular Fertilizer	No of Dealers (n=15)
1	Lakhandur	3	2	5 (33.33)
2	Lakhani	4	1	5 (33.33)
3	Sakoli	3	2	5 (33.33)

(Figures in parentheses indicates percentage of total distribution of dealers towards sale of nano fertilizers and granular fertilizers)

Conclusion

In the Bhandara district of Maharashtra, the study focus on farmers and dealers preference towards nano fertilizers. The findings showed that most farmers have used nano fertilizers in their fields and were aware about nano fertilizers. The adoption of nano fertilizers is higher among educated farmers, with many having higher secondary education or more. Price, availability, and brand reputation are crucial factors influencing farmers decision in purchasing nano fertilizers. Most farmers perceive the price of nano fertilizers as moderate and are satisfied with good results of nano fertilizers in field as compared to granular fertilizers. Timely availability is also important, with the majority of farmers considering cost-saving benefits. Dealers preference and perception play important role in deciding purchase behaviour of farmers. Dealers show a good response towards nano fertilizers, citing good sales and positive results compared to granular fertilizers. However, concerns about availability and pricing still exist for some dealers. Some farmers faced problems in application of nano fertilizers in the field.

References

1. . **Anubhav Singh Baghel, Jayant Zechariah, Nitin Barker, Amit Singh Karchuli, Devendra Mani Tripathi, 2022**, Constraints Faced By The Farmers And Dealers In Marketing Of Vnr Paddy Seeds In Sonbhadra District Of Uttar Pradesh, Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxxiii, July 2022 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601,Page 152-154.
2. **Kumar P., Naib, S.D., Pandey, R. and Sharma, G., 2022**. Efficacy of Emerging Plant Nutrition Sources as Alternative/Supplement to the Conventional Nutrient Sources. *Indian Journal of Fertilisers*, 18(10), pp.974-988.
3. **Kumar, Y., 2021**. Sales Promotion and Marketing Strategy of Nano Urea (liquid) *Indian Journal of Fertilizers* 17 (9) :882-891 Indian Farmers Fertilizers Cooperative Limited Fertilizer Association of India New Delhi.
4. **Kumar, Y., Tiwari, K.N., Singh, T. and Raliya, R., 2021**. Nanofertilizers and their role in sustainable agriculture. *Annals of Plant and Soil Research*, 23(3), pp.238-255.
5. **Kumar Y , Singh T, Raliya R , Tiwari K. N., 2021**. Nano fertilizers for sustainable crop production, higher nutrient use efficiency and enhanced profitability *Indian Journal of Fertilizers Indian Farmers Fertilizers Cooperative Limited New Delhi*.
6. **Kushwaha, R., Dayal, G., 2023**. Application of nano DAP *The Agriculture Publication The Agriculture Publication Volume-2, Issue-8, Jaipur*.
7. **Lahari, S., 2022**. Comparative Study of Traditional and Nano Forms of Fertilizers on Growth and Yield of Rice (*Oryza*

talukas is also equal (33.33% each). Overall, a majority of dealers (66.67%) prefer nano fertilizers over granular fertilizers.

Dealers in Bhandara district have shown a strong preference for selling nano fertilizers due to increasing farmer demand and positive feedback on their effectiveness. The reduced bulk of nano fertilizers, compared to traditional fertilizers, has also made it easier for dealers to manage inventory and distribution. Nano fertilizers are perceived as beneficial both for profitability and environmental sustainability, leading to their promotion by dealers.

In summary, across all three talukas, the majority of dealers showed a preference for selling nano fertilizers over granular fertilizers, with Lakhani showing the strongest inclination toward nano fertilizers.

Sativa L.) (Doctoral Dissertation, Professor Jayashankar Telangana State Agricultural University, Hyderabad).

8. **Mohan S, Reggati V, Arigela A., 2022**. Applications of nano fertilizers in Indian agriculture *Agriculture and Food E-Newsletter Volume 04 Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, ANGRAU, Bapatla*.
9. **Singh, M.D., 2017**. Nano-fertilizers is a new way to increase nutrients use efficiency in crop production. *International Journal of Agriculture Sciences*, ISSN, 9(7), pp.0975-3710.
10. **Swathi, S., Ravikumar, C., Naveenkumar, S., Senthilvalavan, P. and Manivannan, R., 2022**. Consequences of Nano fertilizers usage in agriculture-A Little Review. *Res Agricsci technol*, 3.
11. **Vishakha, K., Deepa, N., Rohini, A., Vidhyavathi, A. and Ravikumar, R., 2023**. Awareness and Perception of Farmers and Dealers on Nano Urea in Gondia District of Maharashtra, India. *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*, 13(10), pp.981-991.